

A User-Friendly Dashboard for Tracking Global Open Access Performance

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Abstract

We identify two issues that obstruct the clear assessment of open access publishing performance by academics, librarians, and other stakeholders. First, the current open access categories are difficult to understand and reason about. Second, there are no easily accessible tools that allow many countries and institutions to view their open access publishing performance. To address the first issue, we have re-designed the open access categories using descriptive category names rather than opaque colour names, re-organised the categories into a hierarchy to facilitate top-down comprehension, and presented publisher and repository-based open access categories without preferencing one category over the other. To address the second issue, we have developed the COKI Open Access Dashboard, an open-source, public dashboard for measuring and visualising the open access performance of 189 countries and over 7000 institutions. We explore the design decisions underlying the redesigned categories and the dashboard.

1 Introduction

Starting in the late 1990s, efforts to make more research outputs available have been gathering pace, following increasing requirements from funders, governments and institutions over the past two decades, changes in publishing business models, and adoption of greater sharing by researchers. Broadly speaking, by saying a research output is open access we mean that a scholarly research output is available online to read and reuse, free of most copyright restrictions (Suber 2012).

Since 2004, a variety of categories have been developed to represent different aspects of open access, including Gold, Green, Hybrid, Bronze, Grey, Diamond, and Black OA (Section 2.2). These categories were developed by many independent authors, each building on the work of the last. As new developments and debates grew our understanding of the place of open access in the field of academic publishing, so too did the set of categories grow with it. The categories are typically represented by a rainbow of colours, metals, and precious gemstones.

Open access is also an area of tension between the interests of publishers, researchers, institutions, funders, and the wider public. In this context, useful debate needs to be supported by usable, transparent, and independent information. While there have been substantial and successful efforts to increase the availability of data on open access performance, most notably through efforts of databases like Unpaywall, the translation of this data into widely usable information has been less successful.

Tools for visualizing open access performance information do not provide academics, librarians, and other stakeholders worldwide, with information to easily assess their country or institutions performance at open access publishing. Some tools allow filtering of publications using open access categories, but don't provide aggregated information at the country or institution level. Other tools do offer accessible open access performance information, but are limited to a specific time period, limited to a specific region, only cover a limited number of institutions, or only consider universities and not other types of research organisations. There are no tools that cover a substantial number of both countries and institutions. Additionally, few tools provide open access rankings and there are no up-to-date tools that focus on visualising open access performance by showing a default ranking of countries or institutions based on their percentage of open

access publications. If a ranking is provided, it is often sorted initially by country name or publication count (these points are discussed further in Section 2.2).

From embarking on a design process to build a dashboard to visualise open access performance, we came to the position that the current open access categories can often be difficult for end users to understand. The following three issues sum up why we believe these difficulties occur. First, the categories are named after colours, metals, and gemstones, which do not convey the meaning behind the categories. Second, there are many categories all presented at the same abstraction level, making it hard to form a top-down understanding of how they relate to each other. Last, the categories have inconsistent definitions in everyday use and their colours suggest conflicting metaphors, often leading to interpretations that publisher open access is better than repository-based open access.

We suggest that this work can be best understood as the following two contributions.

The first contribution is redesigning the open access categories to make them easier to understand. We redesigned the categories using descriptive category names rather than opaque colour names, re-organised the categories into a hierarchy to facilitate top-down comprehension, and presented publisher and repository-based open access categories without preferencing one category over the other. We wanted to present a different way of interpreting open access performance information that was not driven by the assumption that articles available from publisher websites are more important than articles found on other platforms, such as repositories. Other groups have also come to similar conclusions, including the creators of the French Open Science Monitor (Bracco et al. 2022) and the OpenAIRE OpenScience Observatory (Papastefanatos et al. 2020).

The second contribution is the [COKI Open Access Dashboard](#)¹, which is designed to enable academics, librarians, and key decision makers to evaluate their country or institution's open access publishing performance. Our dashboard addresses the lack of country and institution coverage of other tools, by providing comprehensive open access statistics for hundreds of countries and over seven thousand institutions worldwide, with more to come. The data for the dashboard is created by synthesising information from multiple sources including Crossref Metadata², Unpaywall³, Microsoft Academic Graph⁴, and the Research Organization Registry⁵. The authoritative source of Crossref DOIs is provided by Crossref Metadata, open access status by Unpaywall, institutional affiliation and citation count from Microsoft Academic Graph, and organisational information from the Research Organization Registry. Our dataset (Hosking et al. 2022) is frequently updated, enabling policy changes to be assessed in an ongoing fashion.

In the spirit of open infrastructure, design decisions and data transformations are described for the benefit of the community and future maintainers. Instead of claiming neutrality or objectivity, ideologies are stated upfront.

2 Related Work

There is a rich history of previous work on visualising and interpreting open access progress and performance. We begin by providing an overview of the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI) project. Next, we review the history and controversies of open access categorisations and place them in the context of the debates about implementing open access. Then, we examine dashboards that visualise open access

¹ <https://open.coki.ac/>

² <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/metadata-plus/>

³ <https://unpaywall.org/products/data-feed>

⁴ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/microsoft-academic-graph/>

⁵ <https://ror.org/>

performance and discuss common themes and gaps in current tools. Finally, we briefly discuss the limitations of university ranking systems which has implications for the design of the dashboard.

2.1 The Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative

COKI is a vibrant research team of critical humanities scholars and data scientists, working together to build a critical mass of knowledge and capability on the application of open knowledge in higher education around the world (Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative n.d.).

COKI was founded in 2017 by project leads Professor Cameron Neylon and Professor Lucy Montgomery, supported by a two-year strategic research grant from Curtin University. The initial goal of COKI was to develop tools and data that would allow universities to understand how effectively they are operating as open knowledge institutions; and to support strategic change in higher education and research (Montgomery et al. 2021). Over time, COKI has developed into a strategic initiative of the Research Office at Curtin, the Faculty of Humanities, School of Media, Creative Arts and Social Inquiry and the Curtin Institute for Computation at Curtin University, and with additional support from the Mellon Foundation and the Arcadia Fund which has significantly expanded its scope.

Using big data and cloud computing approaches, COKI aims to create the world's leading data set relating to scholarly communication, open access, diversity and inclusion. Our goal is to ensure that the tools and data used to evaluate university performance support more open and productive practices, so that universities can change the public stories they tell about themselves, and to put open knowledge at the heart of these narratives. At the centre of this goal is adopting a critical approach to how we create effective stories from our own data.

In our earlier work, e.g. (C.-K. (Karl) Huang, Neylon, Hosking, et al. 2020), our analysis focussed on how open access performance at national and institutional levels responded to policy initiatives. In this work, we followed existing category names for open access, although we did focus closely on describing in detail how we implemented those categories in our analysis. One of the first public tools COKI developed was an open access dashboard powered by Data Studio that visualised publications and their open access status over time per country, using the existing open access categories of “Gold”, “Green”, “Hybrid” and “Bronze” (described in more detail below). This dashboard was limited to filtering open access statistics by countries only.

Increasingly we found that the shorthand and assumptions that existing categories implied were hampering our ability to clearly describe changes in the open access landscape. The choices made in naming conventions in the 2000s were not serving us well in reimagining what future approaches to open access and scholarly communication could look like.

We believe that open access to research outputs is a single, but important component of an effective Open Knowledge Institution. By providing timely, transparent and useful information on open access performance we aim to support advocates in making the case for change, to provide data for decision makers and to change our shared ideas of what makes a good university. Expanding our initial open access dashboard to include institutions is a key component to achieving this aim.

2.2 Open Access Categories

The categorisation of open access through the rainbow of colours, metals and precious gemstones has a rich history, the product of the debates and positioning of different stakeholders over time.

Harnad et al. (2004, 1) invented the terms **Gold OA** and **Green OA**, describing them in the context of two roads to open access. Gold OA is the “golden” road to open access, meaning to “publish your article in an OA journal”. Green OA is the “green” road to open access, meaning to “publish your article in a non-OA journal”.

but also self-archive it in an OA archive". The colour green describes journals giving "their authors the green light to self-archive". Open access journals and self-archiving started around 1990, long before the Gold and Green definitions of open access (Björk et al. 2014; Gargouri et al. 2012).

Whilst Harnad et al. (2004) originally defined Gold OA to only include open access journals; the term has subsequently been used inconsistently, with some invoking the original definition, (Piwowar et al. 2018; Gargouri et al. 2012; Bautista-Puig et al. 2020) and others adding open access outputs from Hybrid journals to the category, (Costello 2019; Zhang and Watson 2017; Laakso et al. 2011). Hybrid journals are subscription publications in which articles are published as open access under some circumstances, most commonly when the author pays an article processing charge (APC). The remaining articles are 'closed access' and can be accessed only by subscribers (Piwowar et al. 2018). The difference between these two approaches is whether Gold OA is defined at the journal level (original definition) or article level (subsequent definition).

Since 2004, Green OA has evolved to encompass more than self-archiving to institutional repositories, for instance, publisher-mediated archiving to platforms such as PubMed Central or author self-archiving to preprint servers (e.g., arXiv) or domain repositories (e.g., EconStor). Access via other platforms can be to multiple different versions of articles: preprints, author manuscripts, pre- and post-review, and publisher versions that may or may not have the final journal formatting. This access may be associated with delays of various types or occur before or at publication.

Hybrid OA describes articles that are open access at a subscription publisher after the author pays an article processing charge (Piwowar et al. 2018). Walker (1988) first proposed the idea of a Hybrid journal and used it as a model for the Florida Entomological Society (Prosser 2003). Prosser (2003, 164) built on this concept, defining a hybrid journal as a publishing model where authors can either (1) pay a publication charge and "the paper is then made open access on publication" or (2) not pay a publication charge and "the paper is only made available to subscribers".

Commercial journals began adopting the Hybrid model in response to the open access movement, with more pressure building from the introduction of funding agency mandates. This started with Springer & Wiley in 2004, Oxford in 2005, Elsevier and Sage in 2006 and Taylor & Francis, Cambridge and Nature in 2007 (Weber 2009; Boyes and Kingsley 2016).

When Hybrid journals were rare, they were relatively easy to track; however, with a proliferation of new business models for academic publishing⁶, there is now a substantial number of journals which are notionally "subscription" but in which only a minority of articles are in fact "closed". In some cases, fees are paid for publication, and in many cases, they are not. Increasingly publishing services agreements or "subscribe to open"⁷ models cover costs in ways that may not always be visible to authors.

Bronze OA describes articles accessible at a publisher, with no reuse rights. Piwowar et al. (2018, 6) formally defined the Bronze OA category⁸, describing it as "publisher-hosted" articles, which "Unlike Gold OA, Bronze articles are not published in journals considered open access in the DOAJ. Unlike Hybrid, Bronze articles carry no license information. Although this lack of identifiable license may not be intentional, without an identifiable license the articles are free to read but do not allow extended reuse rights beyond reading". There are several practices in which publishers make specific articles or issues freely available to read with no identifiable license; examples include embargo periods where access becomes free after some period (or

⁶ For instance: "publish and read agreements", "read and publish agreements", "transformative[sic] journals", "subscribe to open".

⁷ Where a subscription journal is converted to open access if it has enough subscribers.

⁸ In 2014, Ridgway tweeted the idea of "bronze" open access (Costello 2019; Ged Ridgway 2014).

is free for some period), promotional access for a limited time, and articles made available during crises such as pandemics.

Some definitions treat Gold, Hybrid, Bronze and Green OA as mutually exclusive categories, where Gold, Hybrid and Bronze OA are more important than Green OA, e.g., Piwowar et al. (2018). For instance, if an article is Gold, Hybrid or Bronze OA, the article is not counted as Green OA. A practical reason for making the categories mutually exclusive is that it is easier to create data visualisations. The downside of these discrete categories is that they imply that Gold, Hybrid and Bronze OA are better or more important than Green OA.

Open access via publisher websites has often been treated as more important than open access via other platforms. Assumptions that underly this are that publisher access is immediate whereas repository access is delayed, that repositories cannot host the final published version, and that repositories are less visible to search engines. These assumptions are not entirely correct, but there are historical and political reasons for their persistence. The political debate has led to a false dichotomy characterised by a choice between access via publishers (Gold, Hybrid or Bronze OA) and via other platforms (Green OA). Publishers and scholarly societies have a financial interest in favour of Gold, Hybrid and Bronze OA over Green OA because they receive revenue from Gold, Hybrid or Bronze articles in the form of article processing charges (Gold and Hybrid) or subscriptions (Bronze during the embargo period). As a result, the presentation of open access statistics is often based on the assumption that a publication must be either Gold or Green. It has been rare to present information on how many publications are available through both routes. In practice, a large proportion of open access research outputs are available through both mechanisms.

Open access through repositories is important for policy implementation, including articles that are also accessible via publisher websites. The presence of alternative modes of access strengthens the hands of institutions in negotiations for publishing services and subscription access, particularly with Publish and Read agreements becoming more common. Articles accessible via repositories also provide a safety net for access if publisher access is withdrawn or fails. This provides a controlled archive of an institution's output. For funders, designated repositories have been a powerful means of collating and tracking their funded research outputs. Finally, for publishers of open access content, it can be important to know that copies are available on other sites, particularly where maximising article usage is part of the service they are offering.

Diamond OA describes open access journals that do not charge authors article processing charges. Wilson (2007) first defined this concept as the “‘Platinum Route’ to open access” and in his own later words: “I’ve called this the ‘Platinum’ model, to distinguish it from the well-known ‘Green’ and ‘Gold’, because, unfortunately, ‘Gold’ is often used to cover fee-based publications as well as genuine open access in the Platinum mode” (Wilson 2016). In 2012, the mathematicians from The Cost of Knowledge⁹ proposed a similar category called Diamond OA (Mac Síthigh and Sheekey 2012; Farge 2018). It was initially termed “Free OA”, where “neither the author nor the reader pay any fee” (Farge 2012, 1–2), and evolved into “Diamond OA”, inspired by the “Diamond Sutra, a treasure of the British Library that was printed in 868 in China” (Farge 2018, 74).

Grey OA refers to articles available on websites and academic social networks (ASNs). In their international survey on digital repository use, Nicholas et al. (2012) define Grey OA as the approach of uploading articles to personal websites. They note that three-quarters of respondents who deposited articles in a repository also provided access via their personal or departmental website. Borrego et al. (2016) further refined the concept of Grey OA to mean “if the full text could be accessed at any other website,” including ASNs and personal or departmental websites. ASNs are platforms where researchers can create profiles, network with

⁹ Presumably Marie Farge is also talking about herself when she refers to the mathematicians from The Cost of Knowledge.

other researchers and upload and share their research works; examples include Academia.edu, researchgate.net and Mendeley (Zhang and Watson 2018). Some treat ASNs as their own category without considering content found on personal or departmental websites, for instance, Piowar et al. (2018). ASNs do not make it easy to determine what research outputs they cover¹⁰.

Black OA describes articles on platforms that host pirated copies of publications. The most popular platforms are Sci-Hub and LibGen (Piowar et al. 2018). Björk (2017, 173) coined the term Black OA and described the colour black as “Black as in the classical pirate flag, or in black market!”. Björk’s definition technically includes content from academic social networks in addition to platforms that host pirated content; however, subsequent uses of Black OA typically exclude academic social networks (Piowar et al. 2018; Greshake 2017). In contrast to ASNs, Sci-Hub¹¹ and LibGen¹² both provide comprehensive information about the research outputs they cover.

Whether or not articles in the above categories are considered **Open** or **Closed** is the subject of much debate. Many repositories (Green OA) and all Bronze OA articles do not meet “open access” definitions that require explicit licenses to allow reuse, for instance, The Budapest Open Access Initiative definition of open access (Piowar et al. 2018). Observers of the terminology derived from free and open-source software explicitly link “open” to licenses that allow wide re-use. In practice, most make little distinction between “accessible” in some form and reusable forms of “open”. As a result, all Green OA and much of Bronze OA are often considered as open. The case for Grey OA being open is, well, grey: some consider Grey OA as being open, e.g. (Björk 2016; Archambault et al. 2016), whilst others do not, e.g. (Piowar et al. 2018). The primary reasons for not considering Grey OA as open are that copyright compliance is not checked when authors upload copies to their personal or departmental webpages or ASNs, and there are no guarantees regarding their longevity (Piowar et al. 2018), which is also a problem with Bronze OA. Finally, despite the immense popularity of Black OA (Elbakyan and Bohannon 2017), due to the breaking of copyright most commentators do not consider these articles as open (Piowar et al. 2018).

2.3 Open Access Dashboards

This section provides an overview of dashboards that visualise open access performance, including Open Science Monitor, the French Open Science Monitor, OpenScience Observatory, CWTS Leiden Ranking, Google Scholar and Lens.org. Web of Science, Scopus, and Dimensions are not included because they only allow for searching of publications based on open access status. While they may provide some analysis of open access categories for search results, usually in the form of output counts, they do not display open access performance metrics.

2.3.1 Open Science Monitor

The Open Science Monitor (European Commission n.d.) is a website created by the European Commission, which visualises open access statistics for thirty-six countries, primarily from Europe. The Open Science Monitor began as a study in 2017 and was released as a website in 2018 (Papastefanatos et al. 2020). The website covers publications from 2009 to 2018, using data from the Scopus and Unpaywall datasets. Charts displayed include the percentage of open access publications by country, field of study and publication year; percentage of open access by altmetrics; and number and percentage of funders with policies on open access and archiving, broken down by country. The open access visualisations show statistics for Open Access vs Closed, Gold OA, Green OA, Hybrid OA and Bronze OA (Figure 1).

¹⁰ As far as we are aware the popular ASNs do not provide DOI dumps of the outputs they cover.

¹¹ <https://sci-hub.se/database>

¹² <https://www.libgen.is/dbdumps/>

Figure 1. Open Science Monitor: a selection of open access charts¹³.

2.3.2 French Open Science Monitor

The French Open Science Monitor (Bracco et al. 2022) is a dashboard designed to assess the open access status of French research. This dashboard includes three main components: a general page that provides an overview of all French research, a health page that focuses specifically on French publications in the health field, and institution-specific dashboards for over 30 French institutions.

The French Open Science Monitor is unique because it shows how open access has changed over different time periods, rather than just displaying the current open access percentage for each year of publication. It does this by showing the percentage of open access across various years of publication and across different observation years (Figure 2). In terms of open access categorization, the French Open Science Monitor has adopted a different naming convention compared to the traditional categories. The platform uses the terms “publisher” instead of Gold, “publisher and open repositories” as the intersection of Gold and Green, and “open repositories” instead of Green. The authors chose to represent the intersection of Gold and Green because it does not privilege accessibility through the publisher website over repositories.

Evolution of the open access rate of scientific publications in France, with a Crossref DOI, by year of observation

Figure 2. French Open Science Monitor change in open access rate by year of observation¹⁴.

The general page of the French Open Science Monitor offers a summary of the percentage of open access for each year of observation and the overall growth rate of open access in the past year. It also includes

¹³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-science-monitor/trends-open-access-publications_en

¹⁴ <https://frenchopensciencemonitor.esr.gouv.fr>

information on the distribution of open access per publication year across different observation periods, overall percentage of open access by category for the latest observation year, open access categories by publication type and language, and detailed breakdowns of open access by field of research, publisher, and open repositories. The health monitor has a subset of these charts along with health specific charts, and the institution specific pages have similar charts to the general page, although they differ depending on the specific institution.

2.3.3 OpenAIRE Monitor

OpenAIRE Monitor ('OpenAIRE | Monitor' n.d.) is a service for creating research dashboards for organisations such as universities, funders, and consortiums. Organisations pay OpenAIRE to create custom dashboards that can be public or private. There are currently dashboards for thirty organisations, four of which are public. These dashboards visualise information related to projects, funding, research outputs, open access and collaborations (Figure 3). The visualisations for each organisation are always slightly different; however, in general, the open access section of the dashboard provides visualisations for the total number of open versus closed publications and the number of open and closed publications per year. Some dashboards also provide breakdowns of the previous metrics by publication type and other open access categories, including Green, Gold, Hybrid, and Bronze OA. One dashboard provides breakdowns of top journals and repositories by open access type. OpenAIRE Monitor uses data from the OpenAIRE Research Graph ('OpenAIRE - Research Graph' n.d.) and is updated every 2-4 weeks ('OpenAIRE | Monitor' n.d.).

Figure 3. OpenAIRE Monitor European Commission Dashboard¹⁵.

¹⁵ <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/ec>

2.3.4 OpenScience Observatory

The OpenScience Observatory (Papastefanatos et al. 2020) is an interactive dashboard created by OpenAIRE that visualises open access statistics for 44 countries, primarily of European origin, and a summary page for Europe. The homepage features a map of Europe which visualises the number of open access publications, datasets, repositories, and journals for each European country, as well as aggregate statistics for Europe as a whole (Figure 4). Below the map and aggregate statistics is a table with all countries, default sorted by country name, with the number and percentage of open access publications, datasets, software, and other output types. Users can navigate to individual country profile pages from the table or via a search box. The country profile pages contain aggregate statistics and charts related to open access. The open access charts use an interpretation of the open access categories that treat Gold and Green equally, displaying “Gold OA only”, “both Gold & Green OA”, “Green OA only” and “neither”. The OpenScience Observatory uses data from the OpenAIRE Research Graph (‘OpenAIRE - Research Graph’ n.d.) and is regularly updated.

Figure 4. Open Science Observatory¹⁶.

2.3.5 CWTS Leiden Ranking

The CWTS Leiden Ranking (Centre for Science and Technology Studies n.d.) is a dashboard developed by the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) at Leiden University, which ranks 1,318 universities globally. This dashboard offers information on scientific impact, collaboration, open access, and author gender, but in this review, we focus solely on the open access information which has been part of the dashboard since 2019. The ranking is generated from the Web of Science dataset and refined by CWTS through author disambiguation, precise publication-to-university matching, and integration of open access data from Unpaywall. Rankings are released yearly and are based on material from up to two years prior to the ranking release date. The global ranking section of the dashboard includes a list, chart, and map view. In the list view (Figure 5), users can view universities ranked by total number of publications, with the total and percentage of open access publications as additional columns. The universities can be sorted by the open access columns. Users can filter universities by region, country, and minimum number of publications and modify aggregated statistics based on time period and field of research. The individual institution pages provide more detailed open access statistics, including a tabular breakdown of open access categories, a bar chart of open access (Gold, Hybrid, Bronze and Green OA) by subject area, and a time-series chart of open

¹⁶ <https://osobservatory.openaire.eu/>

access (OA, Gold, Hybrid, Bronze, Green and unknown) by subject area. Users have the option to switch between viewing total publications or percentages in the chart representations.

Figure 5. CWTS Leiden Ranking¹⁷.

2.3.6 Google Scholar Public Access

In early 2021, Google Scholar introduced a feature that allows authors to monitor their compliance with public access mandates from funders (Akash Sethi et al. 2021). The author profile pages display the number of articles that have a public access mandate from a funder and the number that are publicly accessible (Figure 6a). Users can also delve deeper into an individual author profile to see a list of which articles are publicly accessible and which ones are not (Figure 6b).

¹⁷ <https://www.leidenranking.com/ranking/2022/list>

Figure 6. Google Scholar Public Access: summary statistics (a), specific articles with public access mandates (b)¹⁸.

2.3.7 Lens.org

Lens.org (Cambia n.d.) is a search engine with the purpose of locating scholarly works, patents, and academic authors (Figure 7). The author search function offers users the ability to locate and access profiles of academic authors, which presents a summary of the proportion of their published works that are open access (OA Ratio). Additionally, the author profile page includes a list of the authors' scholarly works, indicating which of these works are open access. Lens.org provides profile pages for authors who have registered with ORCID.

Figure 7. Lens.org search engine: author profiles¹⁹.

¹⁸ <https://scholar.googleblog.com/2021/03/track-and-manage-your-public-access.html>

¹⁹ <https://lens.org/lens/profiles>

2.3.8 Discussion

Open Science Monitor, French Open Science Monitor, OpenScience Observatory, CWTS Leiden Ranking, Google Scholar Public Access and Lens.org are free to use. OpenAIRE Monitor charges for creating organisation dashboards, a small number of which are publicly accessible.

Three tools provide a ranking of open access performance, including Open Science Monitor, OpenScience Observatory and CWTS Leiden Ranking. Only the Open Science Monitor ranks entities by the percentage of open access outputs by default. OpenScience Observatory ranks countries by name and CWTS Leiden Ranking ranks universities by publication count (even when the open access indicator is set), with users needing to sort the results to view a ranking by an open access metric. French Open Science Monitor, OpenAIRE Monitor, Google Scholar Public Access and Lens.org do not provide rankings of open access performance.

Open Science Monitor, French Open Science Monitor, OpenAIRE Monitor, OpenScience Observatory and CWTS Leiden Ranking provide comprehensive open access statistics, including percentage and total numbers of open access vs closed, time series charts and breakdowns by open access category. French Open Science Monitor, Open Science Monitor and CWTS Leiden Ranking also provide breakdowns of open access by subject area. The French Open Science Monitor is unique because it calculates and visualises how open access has changed across different observation time points, rather than just displaying the current open access percentage for each year of publication. Google Scholar Public access and Lens.org provide a single open access metric, with Google Scholar showing how well authors are complying with public access mandates from funders and Lens.org showing the percentage of an author's outputs that are open access.

The dashboards collectively provide aggregated open access statistics for different types of entities, including countries, organisations, and authors. Open Science Monitor, French Open Science Monitor and OpenScience Observatory for countries, French Open Science Monitor, OpenAIRE Monitor and CWTS Leiden Ranking for organisations and Google Scholar and Lens.org for authors. French Open Science Monitor, Open Science Monitor, OpenScience Observatory and OpenAIRE Monitor cover a limited number of countries or organisations, with French Open Science Monitor covering France and thirty French institutes, Open Science Monitor and OpenScience Observatory primarily covering European countries and OpenAIRE Monitor covering organisations that have opted to pay to have dashboards created. CWTS Leiden Ranking covers over one thousand universities worldwide. Google Scholar and Lens.org cover a large number of authors worldwide.

Most of the systems use the traditional open access categories. The exceptions are the French Open Science Monitor and the OpenScience Observatory by OpenAIRE, which both use an interpretation of the open access categories that treat Gold and Green equally by showing the intersection of Gold and Green. The French Open Science Monitor goes further by renaming Gold to "publisher", Green to "open repositories", the intersection as "publisher & open repositories" and using this terminology throughout their dashboards.

Most of these tools visualise data that is updated regularly, except for Open Science Monitor, a one-off report from 2018. Open Science Monitor, OpenScience Observatory and OpenAIRE Monitor collectively cover publications from 2007 to the present. The French Open Science Monitor and the CWTS Leiden Ranking release new versions yearly. The French Open Science Monitor covers publications from 2013 to one year before the release date and the CWTS Leiden Ranking includes publications from 2006 to two years before the ranking release date. Google Scholar and Lens.org cover publications from the early 20th century to present.

2.4 University Rankings

Universities, governments, and funders frequently use university rankings and bibliometric information to measure academic and institutional performance, which impacts many aspects of academia (C.-K. (Karl) Huang, Neylon, Brookes-Kenworthy, et al. 2020).

Some of the limitations of university rankings include:

- Features used to calculate rankings may not be suitable measures of university quality (Selten et al. 2020; Billaut, Bouyssou, and Vincke 2010; M.-H. Huang 2012).
- Changes to data sources can cause significant changes to ranking positions (C.-K. (Karl) Huang, Neylon, Brookes-Kenworthy, et al. 2020).
- Bibliometric datasets used for rankings have less coverage for non-English publications and publications from the humanities and social sciences (Montgomery et al. 2020; Aksnes and Sivertsen 2019).
- Previous rankings can affect future rankings, primarily when survey data is used (Montgomery et al. 2020; Espeland and Sauder 2007).

Despite the limitations of rankings, stakeholders still need to understand how well their country or institution performs at open access publishing since understanding current performance is vital for improvement.

3 Design

We designed the COKI Open Access Dashboard to address the issues described above that we experienced with the existing open access categories, and the issues with existing tools that visualise open access performance information.

Our first contribution is redesigning the open access categories to make them easier to understand. The design process for the open access categories was iterative and involved brainstorming, creating low-fidelity paper prototypes²⁰ and discussions amongst COKI team members, consisting of domain experts on open access, a user-experience designer, a graphic designer and software engineers. Our second contribution is the COKI Open Access Dashboard, which is designed to improve on existing open access visualisation tools, by being specifically designed to present high-level open access performance data for the above target audiences so that they can evaluate their country or institution's open access publishing performance. Our dashboard also has comprehensive coverage of countries and institutions worldwide. The high-level design requirements and target audiences for the dashboard are described below.

The high-level design requirements for the dashboard include:

- The visualisations of open access statistics should be easy to understand.
- The dashboard should be easy to use.
- The dashboard should have an aesthetically pleasing design.
- The design should be mobile first, working well on mobile and desktop.

Target audiences for the dashboard include:

- **Academic librarians:** to enable academic librarians to find helpful information for talking to academics and decision-makers in their institution about adopting open access.
- **Academic researchers:** to enable researchers from universities and companies to see how well their institution performs at open access publishing so that they can advocate for change.

²⁰ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/paper-prototyping>

- **Public:** to enable the public to see how their countries and institutions perform in terms of open access publishing.

The design process for the dashboard involved creating low-fidelity paper prototypes, a design brief, wireframes, and hi-fi mock-ups and making sure that they addressed the high-level design requirements and target audiences. We collaborated with professional graphic designer Richard Rigoni, who designed the wireframes, hi-fi mock-ups, branding and infographics for the dashboard. Through all stages of the design, our designer was conscious of the need to create visuals and interactive design components which are sympathetic towards inclusive practice. After the high-fi mock-ups, we implemented the dashboard.

In the rest of this section, we discuss our design decisions in more detail, including our contributions of redefining the open access categories and creating a dashboard to enable academics, librarians, and key decision makers to evaluate their country or institution's open access publishing performance.

3.1 Redefining the Open Access Categories

From our previous experience designing open access dashboards, we have identified a range of issues with the open access categories; these include:

- The categories are named after colours or metals, which do not convey the meaning behind the categories.
- There are many categories. They include Open Access, Green, Gold, Hybrid, Bronze, Grey, Diamond / Platinum, and Black OA.
- The category colours are inconsistent; for instance, there is a mixing of traffic light colours (**orange**, **green**) and medal colours (**gold**, **silver**, **bronze**), leading to questions such as is Gold OA better than Green OA or Green OA better than Gold OA?
- The concept of “Gold OA” open access prioritises research outputs made available on publisher websites above publications made available through other venues.
- When visualising breakdowns of open access, users often expect the subcategory values to add up to 100%, which has often meant that we must choose between prioritising one category over another.
- Categories based on the specifics of licensing are confusing.
- All the above notwithstanding, attempts to argue for a radical change in categorisation have been unsuccessful.

To address the above issues, we have redesigned the open access categories, looking afresh at the categories whilst also avoiding a complete change. It is not feasible to reject the history of categorisation and completely reinvent it, but we believe there is value in refining and re-organising the categories.

Our focus when designing the categories and dashboard was to simplify the categorisation of open access from the perspective of readers of academic works. Another important perspective on open access is the cost of publishing for authors of academic works. We have not addressed the question of author-side costs in this iteration of the design to keep the scope of the design narrow and because of scarce data on author-side costs.

3.1.1 High-Level Categories

We refactored the abstraction levels used to represent open access, using a hierarchy of categories and subcategories (described later). At the top level, we define three categories, focusing on distinguishing between access via publishers and other platforms, the two broad ways a research output can be made more accessible. The high-level categories (Figure 8) include:

- **Publisher Open:** an article published in an open access journal or made accessible in a subscription publisher.

- **Other Platform Open:** a publication shared on a preprint server, an institutional repository, a domain repository, a public repository, or the wider internet.
- **Closed:** a publication that is not accessible, that is, it is not assigned to either of the first two categories.

Figure 8. High-level open access categories.

The above approach allows us to use descriptive terminology instead of opaque colour names by re-organising the existing colour names into the three new categories. Publisher Open encapsulates Gold, Hybrid and Bronze OA, and Other Platform Open²¹ encapsulates Green and Grey OA. The use of hierarchy helps people form a top-down, summarised understanding of complicated subjects, and is often used in software development (modularity) and software engineering diagrams (Moody 2009; Flood and Carson 1993; Nordbotten and Crosby 1999). For instance, it is easier to understand the three top-level categories of Publisher Open, Other Platform Open and Closed than the six traditional categories Gold, Green, Hybrid, Bronze, Grey OA and Closed, which have no explicit hierarchy. This refactoring also allows us to adopt the standard colours for the new categories, so those familiar with the existing categories can broadly match the colours they know with the new ones²². The term “Gold OA” is avoided due to inconsistent definitions, sometimes describing open access journals only and sometimes including the Hybrid category.

In addition to the use of hierarchy, we explicitly show a category of outputs accessible via “Both” Publisher Open and Other Platform Open (Figure 9). We believe this is important to emphasise that Publisher and Other Platform Open operate in parallel and that one is not more important than the other. This distinction contrasts with other interpretations that privilege Gold OA over Green OA, e.g. (Piwowar et al. 2018). As Piwowar et al. (2018, 16) argue, the intersection between Gold OA and Green OA provides a “useful safety net that preserves access in cases where publishers rescind it”, which could occur with Bronze OA articles. The other advantage of our design is that the categories add up to 100%, addressing a common user expectation and making it feasible to create stacked area or bar charts (Figure 9).

²¹ We originally used the term “Author Open” before “Other Platform Open”, however, as noted in Section 2.2 which discusses the open access categories, Green OA has become much broader than author self-archiving, also encompassing publisher-mediated archiving for instance.

²² Whilst the category colours are not ideal, because the colour gold has connotations of being better than green, there is a trade-off between choosing colours with appropriate metaphors and making it easy for those familiar with the existing categories to match the colours they know with the new category names.

Figure 9. Open access breakdown.

Table 1 describes the finer details of the high-level open access categories, including their significance and the mapping to the existing open access categories.

Table 1. High-level open access categories.

Category	Description	Significance	Mapping
Publisher Open	An article published in an open access journal or made accessible in a subscription publisher.	The final edited publication can be read directly from the publisher’s website.	The sum of Gold, Hybrid and Bronze OA.
Other Platform Open	A publication shared online: on a preprint server, an institutional repository, a domain repository, a public repository, an academic staff page or on an academic social network.	Making articles Other Platform Open is free and may be done for historic and new articles.	The sum of Green and Grey OA.
Closed	A publication that is not either Publisher Open or Other Platform Open.	To increase access to academic research, the focus should be on making these publications accessible by uploading copies to repositories.	Not Open. Closed or Closed Access.

3.1.2 Publisher Open Subcategories

After creating the high-level open access categories, we designed informative subcategories within Publisher Open and Other Platform Open.

We divide Publisher Open into the following subcategories:

- **Open Access Journal:** an article published in an open access journal.
- **Hybrid:** an article accessible at a subscription publisher with an open license.
- **No Guarantees:** an article accessible at a subscription publisher with no reuse rights.

Like the high-level categories, the above subcategories use descriptive names rather than colours, which are easier to understand than colour names without inherent meaning. “Open Access Journal” corresponds to the interpretation of Gold OA that does not include Hybrid OA publications, with a more descriptive name. We retain the term “Hybrid OA” for openly licensed articles in subscription journals as we felt this was descriptive. We also renamed the category of Bronze OA to “No Guarantees”, the mixed set of free-to-read but not openly licensed articles in subscription journals. We recognise that this name may not be as clear as it should be and are open to improvements. The Publisher Open subcategories are mutually exclusive, also having the advantage of summing to 100%, addressing a common user expectation and making them easy to visualise.

Table 2 describes the finer details of the Publisher Open subcategories, including their significance and the mapping to existing open access categories.

Table 2. Publisher Open subcategories.

Category	Description	Significance	Mapping
Open Access Journal	An article published in an open access journal.	To qualify as an Open Access Journal there must be clear reuse rights, and the journal must be eligible for the Directory of Open Access Journals.	Interpretations of Gold OA that do not include Hybrid OA.
Hybrid	An article accessible at a subscription publisher with an open license, e.g., a creative commons license.	A route to making articles available in subscription journals that are not fully open access. It almost always involves payment of an article processing charge (APC) or some form of institutional payment through a “read and publish” agreement.	Hybrid OA.
No Guarantees	An article accessible at a subscription journal with no reuse rights.	Publishers sometimes make articles available for limited periods or make them accessible after an embargo period, but without an open license. No Guarantees makes more articles readable but does not ensure long-term accessibility; for instance, the reader has no rights to upload the article to a repository.	Bronze OA.

The goal of having mutually exclusive categories was one reason for not including a category relating to charges (APCs). “Diamond” or “Platinum” is usually, but not always, described as a subset of open access journals. In part this is because it is possible to identify open access journals in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) that do not charge APCs. Detecting articles in hybrid journals for which APCs were not paid is more challenging. Alongside this there are many free-to-read journals that are not in the DOAJ and many of these do not charge APCs. This combination of complexity and the completeness of data led us to not include author-side costs as a category in the current version of the dashboard. We welcome community commentary on how best to include this kind of information to improve the usefulness for authors and those working to drive adoption of low-cost publishing options.

3.1.3 Other Platform Open Subcategories

We divide Other Platform Open into the following informative subcategories:

- **Institution:** publications placed in institutional repositories, including those shared amongst multiple institutions.
- **Preprint:** publications deposited on servers that do not make claims about formal peer review.
- **Domain:** publications from domain repositories, also known as disciplinary or subject repositories.
- **Public:** publications from repositories that researchers from any domain can use and deposit any form of output, including preprints, published manuscripts and datasets.
- **Other Internet:** publications deposited on the wider internet, including publications on academic staff pages, blogs and academic social networks such as academia.edu and researchgate.net.

The Other Platform Open subcategories also use descriptive names rather than colours, which are easier to understand than colour names without inherent meaning. A key difference from Publisher Open is that the Other Platform Open subcategories are not mutually exclusive, as research outputs can appear on multiple platforms and as multiple versions. For instance, a copy could be in an institutional repository and on an academic’s staff webpage.

We have renamed “Grey OA to “Other Internet”, which includes articles from academic staff pages, academic social networks, and the wider internet. Other Internet is included as a subcategory to be consistent with Publisher Open, including No Guarantees; just as a publisher can remove No Guarantees articles with no warning, Other Internet articles can also disappear with no warning. For instance, publishers sometimes perform large takedowns of infringing articles from academic social networks (Piwowar et al. 2018). We do not directly track outputs from academic staff pages; however, we use Unpaywall, which indexes CiteSeerX, which in turn indexes academic staff pages. We also do not currently track data from academic social networks.

Table 3 describes the finer details of the Other Platform Open subcategories, including their significance.

Table 3. Other Platform Open subcategories.

Category	Description	Significance
Institution	Publications placed in institutional repositories, which are archives for storing and distributing an institution’s research outputs. Includes repositories shared amongst multiple institutions.	Institutions can take responsibility for archiving their research, ensure awareness of their research outputs, and leverage institutional policies, including rights retention approaches.
Preprint	Publications deposited on servers that do not make claims about formal peer review. Generally non-peer reviewed manuscripts, including working papers on arXiv, bioRxiv, SSRN, RePEc.	In many disciplines, preprints or working papers are a significant mode of dissemination. Using preprint servers also enables post-release peer review and often offers an alternate route to increasing access which is easier than formally published versions.
Domain	Publications from domain repositories, also known as disciplinary or subject repositories. A domain repository contains publications from a specific subject area. Examples include PubMed Central, Europe PMC and EconStor.	The large domain repositories with roots in biomedical sciences, PubMed Central and Europe PMC are significant drivers of access, often linked to their use within the policy requirements for funders that were early movers on open access.
Public	Publications from repositories that researchers from any domain can use and deposit any form of output, including preprints, published manuscripts and datasets. Semantic Scholar, Figshare and Zenodo are a few examples.	Free and public repositories are an increasing medium for releasing research materials, including those beyond the traditional research paper. Where they are explicitly used for providing access to formally published (or intended to be published) materials, they can be used to host both pre-peer review manuscripts (“preprints”) or post-review manuscripts.
Other Internet	Publications deposited on the wider internet, including publications on academic staff pages, blogs and academic social networks such as academia.edu and researchgate.net. We do not directly track outputs from academic staff pages; however, we use Unpaywall, which indexes CiteSeerX, which in turn indexes academic staff pages. We do not currently track data from academic social networks.	It is still common to find outputs in many places. These sources are generally not archived or reliable for the long term, so we do not count them in the more reliable platform categories.

3.2 Country and Institution Tables

The dashboard homepage on the COCI Open Access Dashboard contains country and institution tables separated by tabs (Figure 10). The table design allows users to see and compare many countries or institutions simultaneously, known as juxtaposability (Green and Petre 1996).

The information displayed in table rows often use dual coding, combining text and pictures to convey information more effectively (Moody 2009). The flag, country name, logo, and institution name enable easy identification of each country and institution. The textual percentage and small doughnut chart provide a dual-coded view of the open access percentage, the most important metric on our dashboard.

Figure 10. The COCI Open Access Dashboard country table.

The breakdown sparkline bar charts provide a glance view of the high-level open access categories within the index table. The total number of publications and the number of open publications are valuable information for interpreting the results in context and for feedback when filtering. The Learn More buttons provide an explicit cue that it is possible to navigate to details pages, as users are sometimes unaware that table rows are clickable. Lastly, most columns are sortable to enable exploration in multiple dimensions.

Considering the limitations of rankings discussed in Section 2.4, we made two design decisions in the index tables to de-emphasise the ranking concept. The first design decision is to not assign a definitive numerical ranking to countries and institutions, as users should not be concerned with their exact rank in the dashboard. For instance, a country or institution’s exact place in the dashboard could change depending on the data sources we use. The second design decision is to not enable sorting of the index tables by citation count, as the dashboard’s purpose is not to create an academic performance index.

A typical pattern when visualising tables in mobile format is to convert each table row into a card and to collapse the columns for the given row into multiple rows within the card (Hoover 2020), as illustrated in Figure 11. This pattern reduces the juxtaposability and the visibility of information in table rows, making it difficult for users to skim, view quickly, and compare data throughout the table (Hoover 2020).

(a)

ID	Country	Open	Total Publications	Open Publications
1	Mali	84%	3867	3235
2	Indonesia	81%	309959	250112
3	Dominican Republic	80%	1368	1088
4	Peru	78%	38970	30559
5	El Salvador	78%	3071	2389

(b)

ID	1
Country	Mali
Open	84%
Total Publications	3867
Open Publications	3235
ID	2
Country	Indonesia
Open	81%
Total Publications	309959
Open Publications	250112

Figure 11. Typical mobile table pattern: desktop view (a), collapsed mobile view (b).

In contrast to the mobile table pattern discussed above, our tables maintain juxtaposability and visibility (Green and Petre 1996) when displayed on mobile screens, as illustrated in Figure 12. This design decision ensures that the essential information is always visible: the country/institution column, the open access percentage, and the open access breakdown. Users can scroll vertically to see more rows and horizontally to see more columns. The country/institution column is always visible (a sticky column) so that data from other columns can always be associated with a specific country or institution.

3.3 Filters

Filters are available to narrow down the items in the country and institution tables so that users can make intelligent, meaningful comparisons between countries or institutions. Figure 13 illustrates the desktop country and institution filters. Users can filter on region, subregion, open access percentage, total publications, total open publications, and institution type. The filters in the open access accordion, including open access percentage, total publications, and total open publications, each have a histogram to help users understand the distribution of items when filtering. We transform the total publications and total open publications histogram and range slider data to be more like normal distributions because it makes the range sliders easier to use.

Figure 12. Mobile country tables: left horizontal scroll (a), sticky country column & right horizontal scroll (b).

Figure 13. Desktop country and institution filters.

The main difference for filters on mobile is that they appear in a modal window popup (Figure 14) after clicking the filter button in the tab header row (Figure 12). The modal window provides more space, having a trade-off of no visibility or juxtaposability of the index tables. The filter button on mobile is a part of the tab headers (Figure 12) to make it clear that filtering functionality exists.

Figure 14. Mobile filters: country filters (a), institution filters (b).

3.4 Search

The search bar at the top right corner of the page enables users to find the details page for a specific country or institution. One may search for countries with country or region names and institutions with institution names, regions, countries, or acronyms. For instance, if one types: “New Zealand”, then New Zealand and its institutions will be listed; “Oceania”, Oceanic countries and institutions will be listed; and “ANU”, Australian National University, will appear in the search results (Figure 13).

Figure 15. Country or institution search: searching for a country (a). Searching for a region (b). Searching via an acronym (c).

3.5 Detail Pages

The detail pages provide comprehensive open access statistics for each country and institution (Figure 16 and Figure 17). The broad categories of the information displayed on this page include metadata and high-level statistics about the country or institution, the open access breakdown, percentage, and volume of open access over time, breakdowns of the Publisher and Other Platform Open subcategories, and Other Platform locations.

Figure 16. Curtin University details page: top half.

There is a subtle distinction to be aware of when interpreting time series charts. The charts show how well a country or institution is *currently* performing at making publications from different years open access. Technically, the charts *do not* show how well a country or institution performed at open access publishing *in years before the present time*²³. However, it can be interpreted as a rough estimate of past performance because institutions typically do not focus on making historic publications open access, although they should!

For example, in the percentage of open access over time chart in Figure 16, 61% of publications from 2010 are closed access. If Curtin University made all publications from 2010 open access today, the value for 2010 would change to 100%. It does not mean that in 2010 61% of publications were closed.

Figure 17 illustrates the Publisher Open and Other Platform Open subcategory breakdown charts. We use a pie chart visualisation for Publisher Open to emphasise that its subcategories are parts of a whole, adding up to 100%. We use a bar plot for Other Platform Open because this is a more suitable visualisation when percentages do not add up to 100% and when there are more categories to visualise (Healy n.d.). We sort the items from highest to lowest and use icons rather than different shades of green, as this makes the bar plot easier to interpret.

The Other Platform Locations table (Figure 17) shows what repositories a given country or institution uses, their platform types, and

²³ Unfortunately, this is a limitation of the datasets and the process we use, we hope to address this in the future, as it is important to calculate open access publishing improvement.

which are the most popular. The table is filterable by platform type, or it can just show the repositories belonging to the given institution.

The Other Platform Locations table (Figure 17) shows what repositories a given country or institution uses, their platform types, and which are the most popular. The table is filterable by platform type, or it can just show the repositories belonging to the given institution.

An infrequent, persistent problem is that an institution’s repository may be inaccessible due to a login wall, or Unpaywall might not know about the repository. To address this, where we have not found any repositories for an institution and the user filters by the institution’s repositories, we show helper text to explain why this could be and a form where they can correct the problem or seek help.

Figure 17. Curtin University details page: bottom half.

3.6 Information Pages

In addition to the dashboard, the website has several information pages providing extra information relating to the dashboard. These include:

- **Open Access:** for people who want to learn more about open access and those who want to know about the COKI definitions of open access.
- **How it Works:** how we create the data behind the dashboard.
- **Data:** COKI Open Access Dataset download links and schema documentation.

4 Data

The data for the dashboard is created by fetching data about research publications from multiple sources, synthesising the datasets and creating the open access calculations for each country and institution (Hosking et al. 2022; Diprose et al. 2023). We describe these steps below.

4.1 Fetch Datasets

Each week we collect several specialised research publication datasets. These include Crossref Metadata²⁴, Unpaywall²⁵, Microsoft Academic Graph²⁶ (MAG) and the Research Organization Registry²⁷ (ROR). We are using the final MAG release from 11 December 2021, and we are currently moving to OpenAlex²⁸, as MAG is no longer maintained. The authoritative source of Crossref DOIs is provided by Crossref Metadata, open access status by Unpaywall, institutional affiliation and citation count from MAG, and organisational information from the ROR (Table 4).

Table 4. Datasets and their roles.

Dataset	Role
Crossref Metadata	Authoritative source of Crossref DOIs
Unpaywall	Open access status
Microsoft Academic Graph	Affiliation, citation count
Research Organization Registry	Institution identifiers, country codes & other metadata

4.2 Synthesis

After the datasets are fetched, they are synthesised to produce aggregate time series statistics for each country and institution (entity type) in the dataset. The aggregate time series statistics include publication count, open access status and citation count.

The synthesis occurs in three steps, as illustrated in Figure 18:

1. Creating a table of publications.
2. Grouping the publications by entity type and year of publication.
3. Computing aggregated summaries for each group. Each step of the process is explained below with examples.

Figure 18. COKI dataset analysis pipeline.

The table of publications is created by joining records from the research publication datasets on Crossref Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), unique digital identifiers given to most scholarly publications. Publications

²⁴ <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/metadata-plus/>

²⁵ <https://unpaywall.org/products/data-feed>

²⁶ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/microsoft-academic-graph/>

²⁷ <https://ror.org/>

²⁸ <https://openalex.org/>

without a Crossref DOI, including those registered through DataCite, CRKN and other DOI registration agencies are currently not included. The dataset therefore has the best coverage for journal articles in English.

Using a single publication as an example, Figure 19 shows how each dataset contributes to the publications table throughout the joining process. Unique publications are identified with Crossref Metadata, each publication’s open access status is calculated from Unpaywall, and each publication’s citation count, authors and institutional affiliations are determined with MAG. Finally, ROR is used to enrich the institutional affiliation records with institution details and map institutions to countries and regions. The ROR assignment of country codes to institutions is used.

Figure 19. How each dataset contributes to the publications table.

Once the publications table is created, the publications are grouped by entity type and publication year; for instance, as shown in Figure 20 below, publications are grouped by institution and publication year. The last step involves creating aggregate time series statistics based on the yearly groups of publications.

Figure 20. How the publications table is created.

4.3 Open Access Calculations

The Unpaywall dataset is used to calculate open access status; the calculations for Publisher Open, Other Platform Open and Closed Access are described in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Open access status calculations.

Category	Description	Unpaywall Query Details
Publisher Open	An article published in an open access journal or made accessible in a subscription journal.	Where the Unpaywall journal_is_in_doaj field is True or where the Unpaywall best_oa_location location_type field is “publisher”.
Other Platform Open	A publication shared online: on a preprint server, a university library repository, a domain repository, an academic staff page or on a website such as researchgate.net or academic.edu.	Any article where any oa_location element in the Unpaywall data has the location_type “repository”.
Closed	A publication that is not either Publisher Open or Other Platform Open.	Where journal_is_in_doaj is False and best_oa_location is null.

The calculations for the Publisher Open subcategories are described in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Publisher Open subcategory calculations.

Category	Description	Unpaywall Query Details
Open Access Journal	An article published in an open access journal.	We use the journal_is_in_doaj tag from Unpaywall to define this category which requires that there be some licensing information provided.
Hybrid	An article accessible at a subscription journal with an open license, e.g., a creative commons license.	We check that the licence field for the best_oa_location is not null and journal_is_in_doaj is False. This includes the value of “implied_oa” which covers cases where publishers have a general assertion of a licence, but it is not clear from the page.
No Guarantees	An article accessible at a subscription journal with no reuse rights.	All cases where the best_oa_location is “publisher”, the licence field is null, and journal_is_in_doaj is False.

The calculations for the Other Platform Open subcategories are described in Table 7 below.

Table 7. Other Platform Open subcategory calculations.

Category	Description	Query Details
Institution	Publications placed in institutional repositories, which are archives for storing and distributing an institution’s research outputs. Includes repositories shared amongst multiple institutions.	Where we have manually matched a repository to an institution, or where oa_locations.repository_institution matches a ROR id with the ROR affiliation matcher, or where the domain from the pmh_id field matches a link from a ROR record.
Preprint	Publications deposited on servers that do not make claims about formal peer review. Generally non-peer reviewed manuscripts, including working papers on arXiv, bioRxiv, SSRN, RePEc.	Where we have manually classified a repository as a preprint server.
Domain	Publications from domain repositories, also known as disciplinary or subject repositories. A domain repository contains publications from a specific subject area. Examples include PubMed Central, Europe PMC and EconStor.	Where we have manually classified a repository as a domain repository.
Public	Publications from repositories that researchers from any domain can use and deposit any form of output, including preprints, published manuscripts	Where we have manually classified a repository as a public repository.

	and datasets. Semantic Scholar, Figshare and Zenodo are a few examples.	
Other Internet	Outputs on sites we have not classified. In practice, these are copies identified by CiteSeerX, which Unpaywall indexes. It may include publications on academic staff pages, blogs and social networks. We do not directly track outputs on platforms such as academia.edu and researchgate.net.	Outputs found on CiteSeerX, which often point to academic staff pages and blogs. We do not currently track outputs from academic social networks. It also includes outputs from repositories that we have not yet classified.

5 Web Application Architecture

The dashboard uses a static site generation architecture²⁹, whereby a program generates all the dashboard’s web pages ahead of time and then stores and delivers the fully rendered pages with a Content Delivery Network (CDN). Once the user has loaded the web page in their browser, it transforms into a single-page web application with dynamic client-side navigation and rendering.

We chose a static site generation architecture for the following reasons:

1. Pages are quick to display in the user’s browser.
2. Dynamic user experience.
3. Users can find countries and institutions via search engines.
4. Cheap to run and easy to maintain.
5. It can scale to many users.

1) Pages are quickly displayed in the user’s browser because they are already rendered and can display without JavaScript, unlike traditional single-page applications. Pages are quick to fetch as a server does not need to render them. Lastly, CDNs deliver content with edge servers close to users, meaning content reaches users quickly.

2) Users have the same dynamic user experience as a single-page application. After the initial page is loaded, the web application transforms into a single-page web application with client-side navigation³⁰.

3) The country and institution pages can be discovered via search engines such as Google and Bing because all the pages are pre-rendered as HTML and are easy for search engines to parse. Additionally, unlike many client rendered applications, the website can be archived and viewed on the Internet Archive, keeping a record for the future.

4) The system is cheap to run and easy to maintain because it consists of a CDN, storage and serverless functions.

5) The system can scale well to many users because there is no bottleneck from a web server or database and a CDN serves the content.

The rest of this section describes the architecture and implementation in more detail, including the web application, the build & deployment architecture, and the serving architecture.

²⁹ Also called a JAMStack architecture: <https://jamstack.org/>

³⁰ This is called “hydration”.

5.1 Web Application

Next.js³¹ is used to build the web application, a React³² framework for creating static rendered websites. We chose React because it is the most popular web front-end framework and Next.js because it is the most popular and feature-rich React-based static site generation framework.

ChakraUI³³ is used to create the user interface because it supports Next.js, enables extensive theming and customisation of user interface components to implement the graphic design, and supports server-side rendering of its components.

We use React Table³⁴, a headless React table library, to create the dashboard tables because it supports server-side rendering, and we can skin the tables with any user interface framework. Lastly, we use both Nivo³⁵ and D3.js³⁶ to create charts as they both support server-side rendering. We use Nivo where possible because it has a higher-level interface and supports React. We use D3.js for more complex or custom use cases, such as the range slider histograms.

5.2 Build & Deploy

Figure 21 illustrates the system for generating data and deploying the dashboard. An Apache Airflow³⁷ workflow fetches data, computes metrics and transforms the data into a suitable format for building the dashboard and uploading to Zenodo³⁸. When the Airflow workflow finishes, it sends an event to GitHub Actions³⁹, which runs another workflow responsible for building and publishing the dashboard website to the hosting provider.

Figure 21. Data generation, build & deployment.

³¹ <https://nextjs.org/>

³² <https://reactjs.org/>

³³ <https://chakra-ui.com/>

³⁴ <https://react-table-v7.tanstack.com/>

³⁵ <https://nivo.rocks/>

³⁶ <https://d3js.org/>

³⁷ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

³⁸ <https://zenodo.org/>

³⁹ <https://github.com/features/actions>

5.3 Serve

We serve the dashboard with Cloudflare⁴⁰, using Cloudflare Workers Sites⁴¹ to run the static web application. Serving static content is fast, low-cost and requires less maintenance because a server and database are not needed. Figure 22 illustrates this architecture.

A Cloudflare Workers⁴² serverless function runs the REST API that powers the dashboard's full-text search and filtering interfaces. These interfaces query dynamic data via the REST API, which stores search indexes in the Cloudflare Worker's memory so that a database is not needed, allowing better scaling, speed and less maintenance over directly querying a database. The full-text search uses FlexSearch⁴³, a fast full-text search JavaScript library.

The static web application content and the REST API responses are cached on a CDN across multiple geographical locations to improve user access times further.

Figure 22. Web application runtime architecture.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The COKI Open Access Dashboard resolves common user experience issues with the existing open access categories and tools that visualise open access statistics for countries and institutions. We have renamed and reconfigured the open access categories to provide more meaningful nomenclature and moved away from the opaque names based on colours. To improve existing open access dashboards, we have made our dashboard free, open-source, and provided comprehensive open access statistics for hundreds of countries and over seven thousand institutions worldwide. In the spirit of open infrastructure, we have described the design choices that led to our changes to the open access categories, the dashboard, the data transforms, and the architectural framework of our web application for the benefit of the community and future maintainers.

⁴⁰ <https://www.cloudflare.com/>

⁴¹ <https://developers.cloudflare.com/workers/platform/sites/>

⁴² <https://workers.cloudflare.com/>

⁴³ <https://github.com/nextapps-de/flexsearch>

For future work on the dashboard we plan to:

- Add more countries and institutions.
- When filtering, update the URL in the address bar to enable users to share filtered views of the dashboard and to fix backwards browser navigation.
- Enable the embedding of a country or institution summary in a webpage.
- Enable downloading of a CSV file with data for a specific country or institution.
- Add more filters, such as the ability to filter institutions by country.
- A variety of usability and workflow improvements.

For the COKI dataset, we are moving from Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) to OpenAlex⁴⁴ for country and institution affiliation matching, as MAG is no longer maintained. Our longer-term goals are to:

- Benchmark and enhance accuracy of country and institution affiliation matching, including multilingual affiliation strings.
- Update our dataset and dashboard to capture change in open access across time, rather than only capturing the current state of open access publishing performance.
- Consider how to support a wider range of perspectives and information, for instance by including information on author-side costs in the dashboard and datasets. We focused on the perspective of readers of academic works rather than authors which means that we have not included categories that relate to author-side costs in this version of the dashboard.

We continue to develop and improve the dashboard and welcome feedback and suggestions.

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